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“THE CANDLES FATE”

No matter how much I like to pretend,
the scars you carry are not mine to mend.

Like a fire you'll flare and flicker,
yet in the wind you never wither.

For a moment, let my hands cover you
From the world that caused such pain
But I know there's nothing I can do
Since I'm melting just the same

I won't lose you, don't go out yet.
Descend we might, but not with regret.
Show all how brightly you burn,
spite them with a passion so stern.

If the world decides to snuff out your spark,
and I watch you melt, my terror stark.
In your final glow, I stay by your side,
for you were the light of my life.